

IMPROVING THE METHOD OF CALCULATING THE LEVEL OF
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES IN
CONDITIONS OF INTENSE COMPETITION

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The summary. The article examines the issues of improving the method of calculating the level of sustainable development of textile enterprises in the conditions of fierce competition in the world market of textile products.

Key words: textile industry, market, diagnosis, sustainable development, integrated indicator, assessment.

One of the important categories of the market economy is competition, and with the help of this category, the mechanism of the market is mainly implemented. It should be noted that now both the method and the form of competitive struggle have changed to some extent, and the main attention is paid to the advantage in the competition. Textile industry enterprises, which are one of the important core sectors of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, export the main part of their products abroad. Foreign consumers have high demands on the quality of products, and in order to fully satisfy these demands, it is necessary to first summarize the available opportunities. *Therefore, in the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the task «to double the production volume of textile industry products» is defined [1]. The successful implementation of such huge tasks in textile industry enterprises, which are one of the leading sectors of the economy of our republic, is important to assess the level of sustainable development based on their superiority in competition by diagnosing the impact of strategic competitive advantages on the sustainable development of the enterprise.*

Practice shows that the sustainable development of the enterprise is formed under the influence of a wide range of factors, but its basis is competitiveness. That is why some researchers suggest evaluating the stability of the enterprise based on its competitive potential [2]. Competitive potential is formed on the basis of competitive advantages. M. in foreign and domestic literature on the theory of competition, management of competitive advantages. Most of Porter's works are cited. All literature on competitive advantage or competitiveness refers to his book «International Competition». In it, M. Porter proposed a set of typical strategies based on the idea that each of them has a unique competitive advantage. The company will be able to implement the chosen strategy if it uses and develops its competitive advantages. For this, the company must decide which competitive advantage to take and in which area: low costs or product differentiation? [3]. Choosing a low-cost competitive advantage means developing, producing, and selling a comparable product at a lower price than the competition. Selling the product at a competitive price allows the company to make a big profit [4].

Sustainability is established in international documents (for example, «Rio Declaration on Environment and Development» [5], «Agenda for the XXI century» [6], as well as the adoption of certain issues of global importance based on conventions and multilateral agreements) and within acceptance refers to the ability of the system to continue to function at the standard level.

The results of the analysis showed that in the case of enterprises in the complex of textile industries, local industrial enterprises, despite their stable development, rarely show positive dynamic development. Most of them are still in a difficult economic situation, and a significant part is in a state of crisis. In this regard, the task of studying the level of stability of the development of industrial enterprises and determining the nature of the impact of strategic competitive advantages on it is of urgent importance.

The results of the analysis of the economic situation of the textile industrial enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan show that in order to ensure sustainable development, it is necessary to have competitive advantages and develop them continuously. Therefore, in order to find the factors and opportunities of sustainable development, in our opinion, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive diagnosis using effective methods in a deeper way.

From our side, we have developed a method of diagnosing the level of sustainable development of textile industry enterprises based on their production characteristics. Based on this method, the diagnosis of the level of sustainable development of textile enterprises includes the following steps:

The first stage «Diagnosis of the level of sustainable development of the industrial enterprise»;

The second stage is «Determining and assessing the existing competitive advantages of the industrial enterprise»;

In the third stage, «Assessment of the impact of strategic competitive advantages on the sustainable development of an industrial enterprise».

As an empirical basis for testing the diagnostic methodology, we have selected several textile enterprises that are members of the «Uztogamiliksanoat» association.

In the process of research, the method of calculating the level of sustainable development in textile enterprises based on the risk component model, criteria and indicator system was improved using an integral indicator. As its criterion, the assessment of the impact of the external and internal environment of the textile industry enterprise on production, economic and economic activities is used. The integrated indicator consists of indicators of strategic and tactical risk factors of the internal and external environment and is calculated using the formula (1):

$$R_x = \sqrt{T_x * C_x} \quad (1)$$

here, T_x – indicator of tactical risk factors affecting the stability of the textile enterprise;

C_x – indicator of strategic risk factors affecting the sustainability of a textile enterprise.

Depending on the type of enterprise, the field of activity, the type of manufactured product, each enterprise determines the most important indicators that describe the level of influence of environmental risk factors on the level of its sustainable development. The information necessary for the calculation of specific and integral coefficients was provided by the studied textile enterprises as a component of the expert's work. The information necessary for the calculation of specific and integral coefficients was provided by the studied textile enterprises as a component of the expert's work.

The results of calculations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Calculated values of the overall integral coefficient describing the level of sustainable development in the textile enterprises participating in the study

Name of enterprises Coefficient value	Name of enterprises Coefficient value
"BETLIS TEXTILE" LLC	0,61
"BEK MEGA TEXTILE" LLC	0,31
"Crystal Color Textile" LLC	0,38
"FULL COTTON" LLC	0,66
"BEST COLOR TEXTILE" LLC	0,76
"COTTON TEXTILE" LLC	0,54

Source: Calculated by the author on the basis of data from reports of textile enterprises.

The data of Table 1 shows that the level of normal sustainable development is typical for «BEST COLOR TEXTILE» LLC. The main component of ensuring sustainable development is a stable economic situation. The value of the private integral coefficient, which evaluates the level of economic stability, is the highest among other private integral coefficients.

Based on the results of the analysis of the existing situation in practice, the main directions for the development of strategic competitive advantages in textile enterprises should include the following:

- anticipating the future needs of consumers of textile products;
- creating a favorable institutional environment;
- activation of innovation activity;
- activation of marketing activities;
- improve the effectiveness of a sufficiently responsive management system;
- improving the efficiency of the management system that can adequately respond to rapid changes in factors and working conditions;
- effective use of digitization technology in all areas on a large scale;
- introducing modern techniques and technologies into production;
- effective use of cost-effective technologies in the organization of basic production;
- implementation of continuous training of employees.

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